

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DATA OBTAINED DURING THE RESEARCH OF THE GENUS *AETHIONEMA* R. Br. IN THE FLORA OF THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC RESULTS

Aliyeva A.

PhD in Biology

ORCID:0009-0009-8075-9490

Nakhchivan State University

Abstract

The article discusses the results obtained during the study of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in 2022-2024. The number of species of the genus distributed in the world, in the flora of Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan and the distribution coordinates in the region are indicated here. Species distributed in botanical-geographical regions of Azerbaijan are listed in the table. Information on the size, life forms, phenophases, altitudinal distribution and ecological environment of the species belonging to the genus is also given. Information on the geographical elements and useful properties of the plants has also been provided.

Keywords: *Aethionema* R.Br., systematics, bioecology, flora, family, genus, species.

Introduction. Research on the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. provides more information on the taxonomic classification, morphological and genetic characteristics, ecology, biodiversity and development of plants. In addition, the distribution and botanical geographical regions of species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. in natural environments in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan were recorded.

Research material and methodology. The studies were carried out from March to the end of September 2022-2024 in areas located in different altitudinal zones of the Autonomous Republic. The object of the study were species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. of the family *Brassicaceae* Burnett. During the expeditions and free routes in the region, the distribution area, systematic composition, bioecological and useful properties of the species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. were revealed. Specimens collected from the study area were identified using various determinants [7; p. 267-268, 10, 11].

The coordinates of the species' distribution areas were determined using GPS Etrex 30 x Garmin. Coordinates at various locations in the region: N38.98954, Eo 46.06562, 2051 N; N38.98758, Eo 46.06594, 2034 N; N38.98721, Eo 46.06553, 2020 H; N38.98660, Eo 46.06562, 2037 N; N38.98668, Eo 46.06517, 1998 H.

Discussion. *Aethionema* R.Br. (*Aethionema* W.T. Aiton 1812) derives from the ancient Greek words "to light, bind, knit". In English it means "stone wall". This name was given to the plant because it grows in rocky and stony areas. The sepals are convex. The flowers are white, pink or golden, rarely yellow. The long stamens are winged on one side, toothed at the tip, rarely all the stamens are simple. The fruit is laterally flattened, round, oval to oblong-elliptic, with or without a winged cap, two-cavity, with 3-4 seeds in each cavity, with an opening, rarely with one cavity, one seed and not opening. They are herbaceous or semi-shrubs with smooth, marginally flat leaves and simple or glabrous hairs. Plants belonging to the genus are bluish, red and pale green in color. Due to their beautiful appearance, some species are used for decorative purposes. There are 60

species of the genus in the world, 12 species in Azerbaijan and 8 species (4.84%) in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. [3; p.185, 8; p.147-157, 2; p.17]:

Aethionema arabicum (L.) Lipsky

Aethionema cardiophyllum Boiss. & Heldr.

Aethionema cordatum (Desf.) Boiss.

Aethionema diastrophis Bunge

Aethionema edentulum N.Busch

Aethionema fimbriatum Boiss.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet.

Aethionema Szowitsii Boiss. (*A. elengatum* auct.)

Species of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. possess distinct bioecological characteristics in the regional flora:

Aethionema arabicum (L.) Lipsky is an annual plant with a stem height of 5-25 cm, notable for its ornamental and fodder value. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may-june, june (july). It belongs to the geographical element of the Near East and is distributed in the dry, rocky, gravelly areas and debris of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema cardiophyllum Boiss. & Heldr. is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 15-25 cm, valued for its ornamental, medicinal, and fodder properties. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may-june, june-july. It belongs to the geographical element of Asia Minor and is found in the dry, gravelly, and rocky slopes of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema cordatum (Desf.) Boiss. is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 10-30 cm, valued for its ornamental properties. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may-june, june-july. It belongs to the geographical element of Asia Minor and is found in the dry and gravelly slopes of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema diastrophis Bunge is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 14-27 cm. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may-june, july-august. It belongs to the Atropatene geographical element and is found in the rocky and gravelly slopes of the middle

mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema edentulum N. Busch is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 25-35 cm. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may, july-august. It belongs to the Atropatene geographical element and is found in the dry, stony, and rocky slopes of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The plant is also a subendemic species of the flora of Azerbaijan.

Aethionema fimbriatum Boiss. is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 25-40 cm. The plant's phenophase period occurs in august. It belongs to the Atropatene geographical element and is found in the rocky slopes of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet. is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 15-30 cm, valued for its ornamental and medicinal properties. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may and june. It belongs

to the Iranian geographical element and is found in the rocky and gravelly slopes of the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Aethionema Szowitsii Boiss. is a semi-shrub plant with a stem height of 20-40 cm, valued for its ornamental properties. The plant's phenophase period occurs in may-june, in may. It belongs to the Atropatene geographical element and is found in the rocky, predominantly limestone slopes of the areas up to the middle mountain belt of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

As seen from the mentioned information, the majority of the species belonging to the genus (7 species - 87.5%) are semi-shrub plants in terms of life form. The majority of these plants are distributed on arid and rocky slopes of the middle mountain belt.

The distribution of species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. according to botanical-geographical regions of Azerbaijan is shown in the table below:

Table

Distribution of species of the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. in botanical-geographical regions of Azerbaijan

№	Species	Greater Caucasus	Lesser Caucasus	Kur-Araz	Talysh	Nakhchivan
1.	<i>Aethionema arabicum</i> (L.) Lipsky		+			+
2.	<i>Aethionema cardiophyllum</i> Boiss. & Heldr.					+
3.	<i>Aethionema cordatum</i> (Desf.) Boiss.					+
4.	<i>Aethionema diastrophis</i> Bunge					+
5.	<i>Aethionema edentulum</i> N.Busch					+
6.	<i>Aethionema fimbriatum</i> Boiss.					+
7.	<i>Aethionema pulchellum</i> Boiss. & Huet.					+
8.	<i>Aethionema Szowitsii</i> Boiss.				+	+

As seen in the table, 6 species belonging to the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. -75% (*Aethionema cardiophyllum* Boiss. & Heldr., *Aethionema cordatum* (Desf.) Boiss., *Aethionema diastrophis* Bunge, *Aethionema edentulum* N.Busch, *Aethionema fimbriatum* Boiss., *Aethionema pulchellum* Boiss. & Huet.) it is characteristic of the flora of Nakhchivan region of Azerbaijan. Studies show that *Aethionema arabicum* (L.) Lipsky is distributed in the Lesser Caucasus botanical-geographical region of Azerbaijan and *Aethionema Szowitsii* Boiss. is distributed in Talysh botanical-geographical region [3; p.185].

Conclusions. As a result of the studies, it was determined that the genus *Aethionema* R.Br. is

represented by 8 species in the study area. Of these plants, 6 species (75%) are characteristic of the flora of Nakhchivan region of Azerbaijan. Four species of the genus belong to the Atropatan (50%), one species to Iran (12.5%), two species to Asia Minor (25%) and one species to the Frond Asia (12.5%) geographical distribution type. One species - *Aethionema edentulum* N. Busch, is a subendemic species of the Azerbaijani flora [3; p.185]. The majority of the genus (5 species (62.5%) are ornamental plants, 2 species (25%) medicinal plants and 2 species (25%) fodder plants [6; p.122-132]. Species belonging to the genus are mostly semi-shrub plants due to their life form.

Aethionema pulchellum Boiss. & Huet. (Kaplanguya 30.05.2024)

Kaplanguya vegetation (30.05.2024)

References

1. Aliyeva A. *Aethionema* R.Br. Representatives of the genus in the modern ecosystem of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic //, Nakhchivan State University, Materials of the I Republican Scientific-Practical Conference on "Modern appearance of Nakhchivan Ecosystem", Nakhchivan, "Geyret", 2023, pp. 46-49
2. Aliyeva A. The genus of *Aethionema* R. Br. spreading in flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous republic of Azerbaijan //, Sciences of Europe (Praha, Czech Republic) No 106, 2022, p. 17-20
3. Askerov A. Flora of Azerbaijan. Baku: TEAS Publications, 2016, 444 p.
4. German D. A. To the species composition of cruciferous plants (Cruciferae) in Russia and some neighboring countries //, Altai State University, prosp. Lenina, d. 61, 656049, Barnaul, Russia, Turczaninowia 25, 1: 2022, p. 146–152
5. Mohamadin S, Peterse K, van de Kerke S.J, Chatrou L.W, Dönmez A.A et al. Anatolian origins and diversification of *Aethionema*, the sister lineage of the core Brassicaceae. American Journal of Botany 104 (7): 2017, p. 1042–1054
6. Nabiyeva F. Useful plants of Brassicaceae Burnett. family common in Shahbuz region //, Nakhchivan Branch of Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, News, Series of Natural and Technical Sciences, Vol. 9, No. 4, "Tusi" AMEA Nakhchivan Branch, 2013, pp.122-132
7. Seyidov M., Ibadullayeva S., Gasimov H., Salayeva Z. Flora and vegetation of Shahbuz State Nature Reserve in Nakhchivan: "Ajami" 2014, 524 p.
8. Talibov T.H., Ibrahimov A.Sh., Ibrahimov A.M. Taxonomic spectrum of the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (Plants with higher spores, open-seeded and closed-seeded plants, II edition), Nakhchivan, 2021, 426 p.
9. Yıldırım Ş, Kılıç Ö. New infrageneric taxa and species of *Aethionema* W.T. Aiton (Brassicaceae) and their current key from Turkey // The Herb Journal of Systematic Botany 23 (1-2), 2016, p. 1–6
10. Zeki Aytac, Atilla Ocak, Bahar Kaptaner İğci Nature guide to plants of Turkey, Ankara, 2021, 752 p.
11. Zeynalov Y., Turkoglu M. Flora of Mount Agri, Ankara, 2016, 402 p.